

MONITORING STUDENT ENGAGEMENT AND LEARNING IN A VIRTUAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENT USING BADGES

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ABSTRACT

A monitoring system embedded into a virtual learning environment (VLE) can assess student progress to ensure no student is left behind. This is significant to support student engagement and learning in a blended transferrable skills and research methods module delivered to over 1,200 students from 15 different postgraduate engineering and business courses at a UK university. Therefore, this short paper addresses the question, “*How can a monitoring system for student progress be implemented in the VLE?*”, through a reflexive evaluation of a monitoring system that recognises individual student’s weekly progress using a series of badges. A badge is awarded to a student when they have successfully completed or passed a set of required learning activities, and it enables students to self-monitor their progress. As a work in progress, this short paper presents a way to implement a monitoring system using badges in a large class VLE, along with an initial discussion about the challenges for implementing this system and the use of this system to prompt interventions. Further research will advance this short paper by examining the impact of badges to motivate student engagement and learning.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Virtual learning environments (VLEs) have enabled engineering educators to gather vast data with which to track and evaluate student engagement, learning, and progress. This data can be used to monitor student engagement, learning, and progress as a foundation for interventions to re-engage students, improve student learning, and encourage student retention [1]. Yet how to design a monitoring system is a key concern. Furthermore, it is necessary to consider how data is gathered to monitor students and communicated to students so they can self-monitor their progress. Therefore, this short paper answers the question, *“How can a monitoring system for student progress be implemented in the VLE?”*

This research concerns the experience of the authors to design a monitoring system to evaluate the progress of over 1,200 postgraduate students from 15 unique engineering and business courses enrolled in a transferrable skills and research methods module at a UK university. Of these students, there are 270 from two courses completing the module for credit. While all students enrolled on the VLE of the module are accounted for in the monitoring system, the research scope is specific to students participating in the module for credit. This blended module is delivered with a strong online component due to the high student-to-teacher ratio since the teaching team consists of four academics, including the authors.

Badges embedded in the design of the module VLE can aid engineering educators to monitor student engagement, learning, and progress in a way that is practical and to scale. This work in progress provides insight into the experience of implementing this monitoring system to support engineering educators to innovate their own VLE to assess student progress in online learning. Further work to evaluate the impact of badges on student engagement and learning will occur at a later stage.

2 METHODOLOGY FOR MONITORING ONLINE LEARNING

Embedded in the VLE of the module is the ‘monitoring system’ comprising of 20 badges, achieved by students on a weekly basis by completing or passing a series of virtual activities (such as group forums, reflective questionnaires, and quizzes). Badges are a form of gamification that motivate students to engage in learning [2]. These tokens are a visual indication of progress that students can self-monitor on their VLE profile. Badges facilitate individuation with each student responsible for their own learning with the aim of achieving all badges [3]. These badges constructively align with the module content in preparation for students’ module assessments. Students enrolled on the module for credit achieve badges as ‘continual assessment’ to promote continued engagement with asynchronous learning [4]. This means a student can earn up to 20% of their module mark by achieving 20 badges (1 badge = 1% of module mark).

The monitoring system is an accumulation of four monitoring points that check student progress during the module and are aligned with assessment dates or term breaks to fit within the student learning journey. One cycle of the monitoring system is illustrated in Figure 1, below. First, a student must complete or pass a set of activities available each week on the VLE. An activity is marked complete when all components have been answered, such as a questionnaire, or passed when a minimum mark has been achieved, as in a quiz. On successfully completing or passing these activities, students earn a badge for that session. Second, students must earn a set of badges to pass a monitoring point. Third, students who do not earn all badges for the monitoring point are sent an email. A student's course leader is also notified by email of students who have missed the monitoring point. Finally, students can continue accessing additional weekly sessions and their activities to achieve further badges regardless of whether a prior monitoring point is complete or not.

Figure 1. One cycle of the monitoring system (Student completes virtual activities in each session to earn a badge and for each monitoring point a student needs to earn 4-6 badges, depending on the monitoring point)

The monitoring system is overseen by the teaching team who are responsible for embedding the monitoring system in the design of the module, technical deployment of the badges on the VLE, analysing badge attainment, and communicating notifications of non-engagement to students and their course leader at each monitoring point. The authors' initial findings of the monitoring system are presented as a work in progress focusing on two themes: challenges to embed a monitoring system and interventions to support student engagement and learning. These

findings are based on reflexive interrogations on the use of the monitoring system. Future work will evaluate the impact of badges on student engagement and learning.

3 INITIAL FINDINGS

3.1 Challenges to embed a monitoring system in the curriculum design of a large class VLE

An initial challenge to implement a monitoring system was the lack of technical ability to design activities. For instance, early session activities focused on a topic or skill rather than in combination due to a lack of technical skills to design complex activities. This resulted in a high number of online activities created for each badge. Some students who were overwhelmed by the number of activities needed to pass a monitoring point resolved this by rapidly clicking through activities. A VLE that includes a high number of activities, or similarly too many materials and links, can compromise deep learning as it undermines the learning experience [5]. Therefore, to avoid surface learning, the team later designed complex virtual activities that included multiple components that weave together many topics or skills to reduce the overall number of activities in remaining sessions. Hence, to implement a monitoring system on a VLE, it's important that module design is informed by technical expertise to create virtual activities that, once completed or passed, form the qualifications needed to achieve a badge.

The team also experienced an additional consequence of the high number of activities used to monitor student engagement and learning: data overload. The teaching team did not have the time and necessary resources available to analyse the extensive data that was captured through monitoring activity completion or marks, so it was difficult to enact strategic decisions to adapt content or delivery of online learning to respond to gaps or barriers in student engagement and/or learning. Therefore, it is important the design of a monitoring system considers the amount of data it will generate and the extent this data is useful for pedagogic decision-making. Hence, construction of a monitoring system must be based on quality rather than quantity of data.

Monitoring points enabled the teaching team to evaluate the extent of an individual's progress to complete or pass learning activities during the module. Yet an issue in using a monitoring point for several badges, rather than a weekly deadline for each badge, is that students achieved a series of badges at the last-minute as evidenced in data captured on when a badge was achieved. While a deadline for each badge was avoided to enable flexibility for students, as some students would be unable to achieve a badge during the week due to conflicts with intensive one-week-block module teaching, it may have compromised the quality of learning. This is significant since the transferrable skills and research methods taught in the module have long-

term implications on students' dissertation and professional success. Therefore, further work is needed to evaluate how students perceive monitoring points and how changes to temporal structures of monitoring, such as a deadline to achieve a badge, would impact student progress.

3.2 Interventions in a monitoring system to support student engagement and learning

A benefit of a monitoring system that can assess student progress is that this information is quantifiable for dissemination to course leaders who can follow-up directly with their students who are not progressing in the module. For instance, at each monitoring point a list of students who did not complete the required badges were identified for each course. This list of students was emailed to the relevant course leader with students categorised as 'incomplete progress' or 'minimal to no progress.' The latter category concerned students who missed the majority or all badges for the monitoring point. This categorisation enabled the team to communicate to course leaders if there were students who may require further support, such as a wellbeing check-in, due to a consistent lack of engagement and learning over a series of weeks. This was a beneficial practice for improving the learning community in which an individual student is supported by a network of staff who are aware of, and knowledgeable about, the student and their circumstances [6]. Yet, further work is needed since it is not clear the extent course leaders did follow-up with these students or the extent course leaders found the communication about the monitoring point helpful.

Students who did not complete a monitoring point received a personal email about their module progress. The email had two key messages. First, the importance of achieving badges as these constructively aligned with the module's summative assessment (as well as counting towards continual assessment). This emphasised the significance of attaining badges as part of learning in addition to engagement. Second, since a lack of progress, learning, and engagement can be due to poor wellbeing, guidance on how to access wellbeing support was included. Many students immediately responded to this email intervention by contacting the teaching team to raise concerns and questions related to their learning experience. As part of an ongoing evaluation of the monitoring system, additional analysis on how the email intervention improved student engagement and learning is needed. For instance, how quickly students began to re-engage with the learning activities following the email intervention.

4 CONCLUSION

In evaluating the monitoring system embedded into the VLE of a module delivered to over 1,200 students, there are two key considerations for practice. First, engineering

educators keen to embed a monitoring system using badges must consider the quantity and quality of activities, as well as the timing of badge achievement, to avoid surface learning. It's also important that engineering educators are provided technical skills training so they can design and implement their own monitoring system. Second, collecting information about student progress in the module can be communicated to students and course leaders to enhance student engagement and learning.

This short paper shares reflexive evaluations by a teaching team to oversee a monitoring system of student progress for a transferrable skills and research methods module. Suggestions for future work to advance this short paper include evaluating the impact of badges to motivate engagement and learning, as well as the impact of the email intervention to re-engage students to learn. Further research would also benefit from evaluating the impact of other forms of gamification beyond badges that can be used to monitor student progress.

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